

The Pros and Cons of Managing Remote Teams

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ABSTRACT: In times when the world was plagued by the Covid-19 pandemic, labor relations underwent new transformations. The home-office presented itself, for many companies, as an alternative to maintain their activities. Supported by an emergency legislation, companies suddenly migrated to the remote mode, which given urgency, needed to be reframed so that the individual could perform his tasks, maintaining, however, the formal employment relationship. This article sought to list the advantages and disadvantages of this modality due to the current scenario, from the perspective of the employee, taking into account personal and professional life. The study evaluated the perception of several companies of different sizes and areas of operation. The quantitative methodology included research through semi-structured questionnaires. The study presented information to enhance the advantages and decrease the disadvantages pointed out. The result was a record of the current scenario that can serve as a basis for decision-making and improvement of the remote modality.

KEYWORDS - Home office, innovation, management, motivatio , work relationships

I. Introduction

The development of technology has favored an increase in the speed of information and communication, which made business fluid and new forms of flexible working relationships had spread, including the home office. The requirements for employees to occupy physical space in the office are no longer as strict as they were a few decades ago. With new technologies, such as telephone mobility, notebooks and the Internet, people can work remotely, from home, on the road, or from anywhere (KUGELMASS, 1996).^[1]

The home office can be seen as a form of flexibility, covering three dimensions, where the first would be the location, as there is no longer a single location, but several places where the employee could perform his function; the second dimension is exactly the flexibility working hours that the employee can dedicate to the task; and the third dimension relates to the means of communication, since data and information can circulate through e-mails, internet, social networks, telephones, among others (MELLO, 1999^[2]; ROSENFELD E ALVES, 2005^[3]).

Due to the current need for social distance to fight the covid-19 pandemic, the home office is no longer an option and becomes an important tool for maintaining activities for many companies. In this way, an individual performs remote work, maintaining a formal employment relationship with an organization.

The modality presents some perceptions of individuals that reflect on their personal and professional life. Selecting the characteristics of this model is directly related to the characteristics of the person, the organization, the resources and procedures made available, work, family, domestic space and society. Parallel to this, the scenario consists of the conditioning elements such as: performance in the company and the effects on the career, the relationship with work, personal life and social and family relationships (BARROS & SILVA, 2010).^[4]

In the modality in question, subjective and inter subjective elements of I-other-world relations are discussed and characterized by the intimate experience of home confinement, it allows observing some dialogues resulting from the personal experiences of the actors involved which in this context contributes to the elaboration and construction of current elements reflected directly in home office since there is no dissociation from personal and professional life, on the contrary, the bond becomes even more intense (PINHEIRO & MÉLO, 2020).^[5]

Understanding the speed of information without associating the individual perceptions of those who make it is simply disconnecting the real from the virtual. One does not exist without the other and that was why home office should be viewed as a context of professional and personal elements. This work presents some visible and quantifiable elements without dissociating the individual from his individual issues so essential in the construction of the environment.

Based on the growing and rapid importance of the theme in recent months and considering the major administrative and structural challenges of the Brazilian industrial sector, the objective of this article was to identify within the administrative teams the common pros and cons of remote work. Finally, more broadly, the purpose of this article is to contribute to the understanding of the main advantages and disadvantages of team management in the home office mode and greater dissemination of the practices currently adopted in Brazilian industrial organizations.

II. Methodology

This article presented a quantitative study with qualitative analysis relating the translation of data obtained through semi-structured questionnaires. The quantitative approach sought to portray the current scenario in numbers and the qualitative approach comprises the fundamental elements for understanding the lived environment.

Semi-structured questionnaires were applied to those by means of an electronic form using the Google Forms tool in workers from different areas. The questionnaire was sent to random professionals via the professional social network LinkedIn and professional groups on WhatsApp. The form was available for responses for seven days and was answered by sixty-eight people.

The questionnaire was divided into four main parts, which are: characterization of the sample, survey of the main changes in the home office modality; employees' perception of the current scenario and advantages and disadvantages of the home office modality.

In the first part, the questions were related to the company's sector, number of company employees and hierarchical level of the respondents. The second part that dealt with the survey of the main changes in the home office modality sought to list the main changes to guide this work, such as: the modality change in the company, the reduction of hours and the offer of training when migrating from modality. The third part dealt

with the employees' perception of the current scenario and constituted questions such as: the team's relationship, the work routine, the production and the main advantages and disadvantages of the modality. The fourth part the respondent, with his words explained the advantages and disadvantages. Understanding that this question could present different perceptions, the question was presented in text form.

III. Results

In Fig. 1, the public identified in this study was mainly composed of employees from companies in the food and beverage sector (45.5%), followed by the education sector (25.8%). Most are employees of large companies (66.7%, Fig. 2), being formed mainly by analysts (37.9%, Fig. 3) and coordinators (27.3%, Fig. 3).

FIGURE 1: Industrial sector to which it belongs

FIGURE 2: Company size of employees analyzed

FIGURE 3: Hierarchical level in the company

Regarding the survey of the main changes in the home office modality, it was identified that 89.4% of the respondents had migrated to the home office modality as a tool to face the Covid - 19 pandemic (Fig. 4). Of

the companies studied, 75.8% opted to reduce working hours with reduced wages (Fig. 5). Of these companies, when migrating to home office mode, 72.7% offered training on the relationship with their teams in the new scenario (Fig. 6).

FIGURE 4: Number of employees who started to work home office to cope with Covid-19 Pandemic.

FIGURE 5: Chose to reduce working hours and reduce wages.

Figura 6: Did your company, when migrating to the home office, undergo any training or give any instructions on the relationship with your teams in the home-office mode?

The last part of this work presents the perception of employees and determined that there was no significant change in relation to the relationship with the team (Fig. 7), 71.2% managed to establish a work routine (Fig. 8) and 59.1% realized better institutional engagement (Fig. 9).

FIGURE 7: Did the relationship with the team get better or worse with remote work?

FIGURE 8: In this modality can you establish a schedule or a routine to work at home?

FIGURE 9: How was the production / institutional engagement with remote work?

In this section, the last of our study, it was about the advantages and disadvantages listed for home office modality. In this regard, it was observed that what for some constitutes an “advantage” for others, the same item was seen from another point of view. Table 1 shows the responses presented by the interviewees regarding Advantages x Disadvantages of the items presented.

ITEMS	ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES
Security	Be safe	
Technological skills	New knowledges	
Company	Fixed expenses reduction	
Schedule	Flexibility	Less concentration

Productivity	Companies increased	Companies decreased
Feeding	Economy	Overweight
Displacement	Economy	Sedentary
Family	More time with family/children	Yield drop - concentration
Interaction		Decreased
Home office infrastructure		Decreased quality
Work load		New assignments without remuneration Higher workload

Table 1: List of Advantages x Disadvantages of the home office modality

It was observed that there are items that are unanimous as to the advantage, such as: security, technological skills and reduction of the company's fixed costs and there are items that are unanimous as to the disadvantages, such as: interaction, home office infrastructure and workload .

In this study, variant elements were identified, such as hours, productivity, food, commuting and time with the family and on this point it appears that it is related to the mode of personal relationships that the respondents lived before Covid-19.

IV. Discussion

This study presented data, in its majority, of companies with more than two hundred and fifty collaborators that even in the face of uncertainties caused by the World Pandemic, was quick to migrate to remote mode. The salary reduction adjustments were an attempt to dilute the impacts generated by the uncertainties.

As for the reduction of wages, its occurrence is not necessarily linked to the fall in production, but in the entrepreneurial opportunity given by the current government. Since many of the respondents declared an increase in workload and at the same time a reduction in money.

The majority of respondents reported that they view the home office as a business benefit for maintaining the economy and we identified that this fact constituted an important element for the motivation and relationship of the individuals who are more productive.

V. Conclusion

In times of Pandemic, listing the advantages and disadvantages of the sport is not an easy task, since the uncertain environment contributes to these attributes to change easily. On the one hand, companies have sought to adapt voraciously so as not to succumb to an act of survival in the market. On the other hand, the workers are receptive and solicitous to attend to the maximum the conditions imposed by understanding that this is the survival of their jobs.

The home office modality was the best proposal for survival on both sides and in this study we perceive a broad effort by both parties to promote conditions of stability. This work suggests that after pandemic the work presents the "mixed" modality in which the advantages of both work systems were taken advantage of.

REFERENCES

- [1] KUGELMASS, Joel. *Teletrabalho: Novas Oportunidades para o Trabalho Flexível: seleção de funcionários, benefícios e desafios, novas tecnologias de comunicação*. São Paulo: Atlas, 1996.
- [2] MELLO, Álvaro. *Teletrabalho (telework): o trabalho em qualquer lugar e a qualquer hora*. Rio de Janeiro : Qualitymark, ABRH Nacional, 1999
- [3] ROSENFELD, C. L.; ALVES, D. A. de. *Autonomia e trabalho informacional: o teletrabalho*. DADOS – Revista de Ciências Sociais, v. 54, n. 1, p. 207-233, 2011.
- [4] Barros, Alexandre Moço; Silva José Roberto Gomes da , *Percepções dos indivíduos sobre as consequências do teletrabalho na configuração home-office: estudo de caso na Shell Brasil* https://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?pid=S1679-39512010000100006&script=sci_arttext&tlng=pt -2010
- [5] Pinheiro, Marina Assis; Mélo, Roberto de Sousa - *DIÁRIOS DE CONFINAMENTO: A EMERGÊNCIA DO NOVO NA INTIMIDADE DA RELAÇÃO EU-OUTRO-MUNDO* - *Psicol. Soc.* Vol. 32 Belo Horizonte 2020 https://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0102-71822020000100410